

Ethical AI Quiz Screenshots:

This document contains the screenshots of the whole [Quiz](https://conf.researchr.org/details/icse-2023/icse-2023-demonstrations/20/What-Would-You-do-An-Ethical-AI-Quiz) as reported in the ICSE paper (<https://conf.researchr.org/details/icse-2023/icse-2023-demonstrations/20/What-Would-You-do-An-Ethical-AI-Quiz>).

Version: 1

Last updated date: 3 Feb 2023

Fig 1: First page

Fig 2: Explanatory statement

Fig 3: Job role

Fig 4: Question 1

Question 2/13
GIVEN THE SCENARIO...

© Shutterstock by Shiroam

You are an AI developer working at a technology firm called Techscape. In order to make the recruitment process easier, the company has decided to develop an AI-based recruitment tool that automatically shortlists potential candidates based on their CVs. However, after putting it to use, it is discovered that the tool disproportionately selects men over women candidates.

How would you proceed in this scenario?

Please select an answer below

Start addressing the issue while continuing the tool's deployment in the market	Ignore the issue and trust the tool to choose the best candidates
Try your best to withdraw the tool from the market	Follow what your supervisor says, even if they decide to withdraw the tool from the market

Fig 5: Question 2

Question 3/13
GIVEN THE SCENARIO...

© Shutterstock by Shiroam

You are an AI developer working at a technology firm called Techscape. In order to make the recruitment process easier, the company has decided to develop an AI-based recruitment tool that automatically shortlists potential candidates based on their CVs. However, after putting it to use, it is discovered that the tool disproportionately selects men over women candidates.

It was discovered that solving the gender bias problem in the recruitment tool is possible but requires additional time, effort, and money. How would you proceed?

Please select an answer below

Decide what to do depending on the effort/time/money it requires	Deploy the tool as it is since the company has already invested time and money into it
Work towards making the tool better even though it may cost a lot more effort/money/time	Recall and de-establish the tool

Fig 6: Question 3

Question 4/13
GIVEN THE SCENARIO...

© Illustrations by Storyset

You are an AI developer working at a technology firm called Techscape. In order to make the recruitment process easier, the company has decided to develop an AI-based recruitment tool that automatically shortlists potential candidates based on their CVs. However, after putting it to use, it is discovered that the tool disproportionately selects men over women candidates.

Which ethics principles do you think are being breached in this case?

Please select an answer below

Transparency	Privacy
Reliability	Fairness

Fig 7: Question 4

Question 5/13
GIVEN THE SCENARIO...

© Illustrations by Storyset

IntelZone is an AI-based company which is developing an AI-based system to be used for decision making in healthcare which is known as AICare. You are one of the AI developers assigned to the AICare project. AICare was deployed in a hospital for use.

A patient went to the hospital for a checkup, and AICare diagnosed the patient with tuberculosis. Next day the patient got a call from a private diagnostic centre offering the treatment at a discounted price. It is the case of a data privacy issue. Who do you think is responsible?

Please select an answer below

The AI developers	The patient
The hospital	The doctor

Fig 8: Question 5

Question 6/13
GIVEN THE SCENARIO...

© Illustrations by Storyart

IntelZone is an AI-based company which is developing an AI-based system to be used for decision making in healthcare which is known as AICare. You are one of the AI developers assigned to the AICare project. AICare was deployed in a hospital for use.

After deploying AICare in the hospital, you found out that AICare gives a diagnosis with a racial bias, for eg: A white patient and a black patient share the same symptoms and same lifestyle; AICare rules that the white male has a cold while the black male has a more severe disease. What do you do?

Please select an answer below

Follow what the majority of the development team decides on	Keep quiet and ignore the issue
Continue AICare's deployment in the hospital but work on the required changes parallelly	Alert the hospital to stop using AICare and investigate the root cause and fix it

Fig 9: Question 6

Question 7/13
GIVEN THE SCENARIO...

© Illustrations by Storyart

IntelZone is an AI-based company which is developing an AI-based system to be used for decision making in healthcare which is known as AICare. You are one of the AI developers assigned to the AICare project. AICare was deployed in a hospital for use.

AICare made a wrong diagnosis which the doctor was obliged to follow. The patient experienced side effects as a result. Who is accountable for this?

Please select an answer below

The AI developers	The hospital
The doctor	The patient

Fig 10: Question 7

Question 8/13
GIVEN THE SCENARIO...

© Illustrations by Starveit

An AI-based company Horizon is developing an AI-based system known as TechnoArt that uses deep learning to create art. It analyses the artist's original art and mimics the artist's unique style to create a different artwork and adds the signature of the original artist to the new work.

Do you think taking an artist's original art and running it through an algorithm to create something similar and profit from it is ethical?

Please select an answer below

Yes, with or without artist consent, but only for restoring unfinished or damaged original art	Yes, without artist consent, whether alive or dead
Yes, without artist consent if dead	Yes, but with consent of alive artist or family/trust of dead artist

Fig 11: Question 8

Question 9/13
GIVEN THE SCENARIO...

© Illustrations by Starveit

An AI-based company Horizon is developing an AI-based system known as TechnoArt that uses deep learning to create art. It analyses the artist's original art and mimics the artist's unique style to create a different artwork and adds the signature of the original artist to the new work.

Who do you think deserves the most credit for the final product?

Please select an answer below

The company Horizon	The original painter
The AI developers and the algorithm	All of the above

Fig 12: Question 9

Question 10/13
GIVEN THE SCENARIO...

© Illustrations by Starvest

An AI-based company Horizon is developing an AI-based system known as TechnoArt that uses deep learning to create art. It analyses the artist's original art and mimics the artist's unique style to create a different artwork and adds the signature of the original artist to the new work.

Most of the art produced by TechnoArt portrays men as leaders and warriors while women come out to be overly sexualized; what do you think the next step should be?

Please select an answer below

- Ignore it as art can be viewed from different perspectives
- Make required changes in the implementation to address the issue
- Refuse to continue implementing the system
- Raise the concern but proceed as the management decides

Fig 13: Question 10

Question 11/13
GIVEN THE SCENARIO...

© Illustrations by Starvest

An AI-based company, Orchid, is developing AI-based software that helps make factory chemical waste management decisions. You are working as the manager on this project. Upon using the AI-based software you developed, one of your customers - a factory owner - found that dumping the chemical waste in the river right next to their factory maximizes the company's profit. The factory owner notifies you about this issue.

What would you do as the next course of action?

Please select an answer below

- Discuss with your team members and go with whatever the majority say
- Recommend them to take the AI's suggestions and proceed with it
- Advocate for a compromise between profit and the well-being of the environment
- Advocate for the most environmental friendly option

Fig 14: Question 11

Question 12/13
GIVEN THE SCENARIO...

© Illustrations by Starveit

An AI-based company, Orchid, is developing AI-based software that helps make factory chemical waste management decisions. You are working as the manager on this project. Upon using the AI-based software you developed, one of your customers - a factory owner - found that dumping the chemical waste in the river right next to their factory maximizes the company's profit. The factory owner notifies you about this issue.

Which ethics principles do you think are most breached in this case?

Please select an answer below

Human, societal and environmental wellbeing	Transparency and explainability
Reliability and safety	Privacy protection and security

Fig 15: Question 12

Question 13/13
GIVEN THE SCENARIO...

© Illustrations by Starveit

An AI-based company, Orchid, is developing AI-based software that helps make factory chemical waste management decisions. You are working as the manager on this project. Upon using the AI-based software you developed, one of your customers - a factory owner - found that dumping the chemical waste in the river right next to their factory maximizes the company's profit. The factory owner notifies you about this issue.

What would be your first reaction?

Please select an answer below

Give no reaction as this is not a major issue	Feel bad that the team made the error and work with them to fix the error immediately
Feel surprised that the team made the error and ask them to fix the error if time permits	Feel angry at your team members and call a meeting to reprimand them

Fig 16: Question 13

Fig 17: Results Summary Page